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TRADE BALANCE, EXCHANGE RATE MOVEMENTS AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA: A DISAGGREGATED APPROACH

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Анотація. Досягнення сприятливого платіжного балансу є однією з основних макроекономічних цілей країни. Досягти цього означає розпочати ефективну політику, яка сприятиме експорту та перешкоджає надмірному імпорту. Такий акт гарантує, що країна досягне сприятливого торгового балансу, який не буде загрожувати балансу поточного рахунку.

У цій статті ми дослідили вплив торговельного балансу та зміни обмінного курсу на економічне зростання в Нігерії, а також детермінанти обмінного курсу за період з 1981 по 2020 рр. Дослідження виконане з застосуванням авторегресивного розподіленого підходу з затримкою для оцінки чотирьох моделей. У моделі I спостерігається позитивний і значний вплив загальної торгівлі на економічне зростання, тоді як обмінний курс має значний негативний вплив. Збільшення загального торгового балансу призводить до зростання економічного зростання на 0,0039%; тоді як збільшення на один відсоток обмінного курсу призводить до зниження економічного зростання на 0,0510%. Друга модель дозволила виявити негативний та істотний вплив на економічне зростання балансу торгівлі нафтою і валютного курсу. Збільшення балансу торгівлі нафтою та обмінного курсу на один відсоток призводить до зниження економічного зростання на 0,0113% та 0,0758% відповідно. У третій моделі виявлено, що ненафтовий торговий баланс чинить негативний і значний вплив на економічне зростання, натомість обмінний курс чинить негативний, але незначний вплив на економічне зростання. Нарешті, Модель IV, яка фіксує детермінанти обмінного курсу в Нігерії, показує, що економічне зростання, зовнішні резерви, інфляція та загальний торговий баланс є основними чинниками обмінного курсу в Нігерії. З отриманих висновків випливає, що стимулювання внутрішнього виробництва для збільшення ненафтового експорту допоможе забезпечити стабільність обмінного курсу, що сприятиме зростанню економіки Нігерії.

Ключові слова: валютний курс, економічне зростання, торговельний баланс, міжнародна торгівля.

Annotation. The influence of trade balance and exchange rate movement on economic growth in Nigeria, as well as the determinants of the exchange rate, is examined in this study for the period 1981 to 2020. The study follows the autoregressive distributed lag approach to estimate the four models specified in the study. In Model I, total trade is observed to have a positive and significant effect on economic growth, while the exchange rate exerts a negative and significant effect. A unit percent increase in total trade balance leads to a 0.0039% increase in economic growth, while a unit percent increase in exchange rate leads to a 0.0510% decrease in economic growth. In the second model, both oil trade balance and exchange rate exert a negative and significant effect on economic growth. A unit percent increase in oil trade balance and exchange rate leads to a 0.0113% and 0.0758% decrease in economic growth, respectively. In the third model, the non-oil trade balance exerts a negative and significant effect on economic growth, while the exchange rate exerts a negative but insignificant effect on economic growth. Finally, Model IV, which captures the determinants of the exchange rate in Nigeria, reveals that economic growth, external reserves, inflation, and total trade balance are the major drivers of the exchange rate in Nigeria since they exert a significant effect. It follows from the findings that stimulating domestic production to boost non-oil exports will help to ensure exchange rate stability that will promote growth within the Nigerian economy.

Keywords: exchange rate, economic growth, balance of trade, international trade.

Introduction

Achieving a favourable balance of payments is one of the core macroeconomic goals of a nation. To achieve such implies embarking on sound policies that will promote exports and discourage excessive imports. Such act ensures that the country achieves a favourable trade balance that will not strain the current account balance. The rising demand for imported products in Nigeria has continued to wreak havoc on the population, forcing the currency to depreciate in recent years. Furthermore, the persistent current account deficits that have required a country to demand more foreign currency than it obtains from export sales have had a negative impact on the economy. The consequences of this practice include, but are not limited to, currency devaluation, trade diversion, job loss in the importing country's home country, low per capita income, and a worse living standard for the inhabitants (Onakoya, Aworinde and Yinusa, 2019). This shows that volatility in trade balances and currency rates may stymie inclusive growth.

An exchange rate policy's aims include selecting an acceptable exchange rate and guaranteeing its stability. Efforts have been made throughout the years to achieve these goals via the use of various approaches and possibilities to create efficiency in the foreign exchange market. Nigeria's exchange rate arrangements evolved from a fixed regime in the 1960s to a pegged system between the 1970s and the mid-1980s, and eventually to different forms of the floating regime beginning in 1986 with deregulation and the implementation of the structural adjustment program (SAP). Since the SAP, the most prevalent floating system in Nigeria has been a managed floating exchange rate regime with no clear commitment to protecting any specific parity (Akpan and Atan, 2015).

The Dutch Auction System (DAS) was re-introduced on July 22, 2002, following the failures of the variants of the flexible exchange rate mechanism (the Autonomous Foreign Exchange Market, AFEM, launched in 1995 and the Inter-Bank Foreign Exchange Market, IFEM, implemented in 1999) to assure exchange rate stability. The DAS was designed to accomplish three goals: reduce the parallel market premium, save diminishing foreign reserves, and create a realistic naira exchange rate (Akpan and Atan, 2015). The DAS aided in the stabilization of the naira exchange rate, the reduction

of the widening premium, the conservation of foreign reserves, and the reduction of authorized dealers' speculative inclinations. Since 2003, the foreign exchange market has remained largely stable.

The external reserve position, which could guarantee adequate funding of the market by the CBN; reduce inflationary pressures; instrument autonomy of the CBN and its prompt deployment of monetary control instruments in support of the DAS, as well as the bi-weekly auctions as opposed to the previous fortnightly auctions, thus assuring a steady supply of foreign exchange, were among the conditions that facilitated the re-introduction of DAS in 2002 (Mordi, 2006).

On February 20, 2006, the CBN introduced the Wholesale Dutch Auction System (WDAS) to further liberalize the market, reduce the arbitrage premium between the official interbank and bureau de change parts of the markets, and achieve convergence. This was intended to solidify the retail Dutch Auction System's gains as well as broaden the foreign currency market in order to provide a realistic naira exchange rate. Authorized dealers were allowed to deal in foreign currencies on their own accounts for resale to their clients under this system. Presently, the exchange rate regime follows the managed float system. Could these variants of exchange rate exert some degree of influence on the exchange rate of Nigeria? Figure 1 displays the exchange rate movements in Nigeria.

Fig. 1. Exchange rate movements in Nigeria, 1981 to 2020

The period 1981 to 1997 was posed with a somewhat stable exchange rate. It averaged ₦2.40/\$1 between 1981 to 1989 but rose significantly to an average of ₦18.53/\$1 between 1990 to 1998. Thereafter, the exchange naira-dollar exchange rate faced a tremendous depreciation by rising from ₦21.89/\$1 in 1998 to ₦92.69/\$1 in 1999. This was followed by a further depreciation till date. Between 2000 to 2010, exchange rate averaged ₦127.48/\$1 with the highest of ₦150.30/\$1 as at 2010; while between 2011 and 2020, it averaged ₦235.16/\$1 with the highest being ₦358.81/\$1 as at 2020 (CBN, 2020). Could it be that this drastic depreciation of the currency is as a result of the declining exports and the attendant unfavourable trade balance which may have a deteriorating effect on economic growth over the years? Figure 2 reflects the nature of trade balance and economic growth of Nigeria. In Figure 2, the oil trade balance is reflected in Panel I, non-oil trade balance in panel II, total trade balance in Panel III, and growth rate of real GDP in panel IV.

Fig. 2. Trends of trade balance and real GDP growth rate

In panel I, the behaviour of oil trade balance is portrayed. It is observed that oil trade balance in the 1980s was minimal and stable till 1993 where it started to rise sharply due to high demand for oil in the international oil market. Meanwhile, there have been series of fluctuations in the oil trade balance due to shocks in the international oil market. Panel II captures the non-oil trade balance where it is observed that the nation has been witnessing negative non-oil trade balance over the years. Though it was minimal in the 1980s and 1990s, the trend has been discouraging right from 2000 where the non-oil trade balance declined sharply till 2020, reaching an all-time low of -17,183,926.74 billion naira (CBN, 2020).

In panel III, the trend of total trade balance is presented. It is noticed that it was negative from 1981 to 1983, before recovering steadily till 1997 before it plunges to -85,562.00 billion naira as at 1998. Thereafter, the nation enjoyed an all-time sixteen years' favourable trade balance from 1999 till 2014 averaging 3,016,923.94 billion naira within the same period. Subsequently, the country also moved into a two-year negative trade balance for 2015 and 2016 before a recovery in 2017 and 2018. Due to the covid-19 pandemic and its attendant economic crisis, the country moved into a negative total trade balance of -8,168,415.84 billion naira in 2020 (CBN, 2020).

As pointed out by Obi *et al.* (2016) cited in Alasha (2020), Nigeria aspires to become one of the world's leading developed economies by 2050. Meanwhile, the present economic situation seems to raise question on the possibility of reaching such goal. The non-trade balance is fast deteriorating and

the international oil market is faced with shocks leaving the nation at a cross-road. Coupled with the Covid-19 pandemic, the socio-economic situation of the country is declining. Since no economy can exist in isolation, the need for international trade becomes sacrosanct. Meanwhile, Nigeria is facing international trade issues coupled with currency depreciation.

Nigeria's currency has recently seen the worst depreciation in its history; the drop in her exchange rate has been attributed to the depletion of her reserves, which has been prompted by the worldwide drop in oil prices (Yusuf, Oyegoke, Gylych and Haruna. 2019). Nigeria, a single-product exporter heavily reliant on crude oil sales, has seen a drop in foreign exchange earnings and is currently struggling to satisfy the demands of its teeming import-dependent population. The unusually wide gap between parallel market and official naira rates is a source of worry for the monetary authorities, who have tried a variety of initiatives to resolve the issue to little avail.

Although it has long been assumed that some key macroeconomic variables determine a country's optimal real exchange rate, and various theories abound as to what typically determines exchange rates, the recent decline of exchange rates has occurred in some cases without any corresponding link to existing macroeconomic fundamentals (Yusuf *et al.*, 2019). This explains why exchange rate determination has recently gained in popularity and attention, as it appears to be one of the most significant topics in the theoretical area of monetary economics. Understanding what drives exchange rates is more important than ever, since knowing its drivers, particularly in a developing country like Nigeria, may help the sovereign monetary authority make better policy decisions.

Review of Related Literature

2.1.1 Theories of Exchange Rate

Three basic approaches are used to explain the link between the exchange rate and trade balances in the theoretical literature – the trade or elasticity approach, the absorption approach, and the monetary approach. Consistent with the elasticity approach, the effect of devaluation on trade balance is determined by the elasticity of imports and exports. This theory's proponents believe that a short-term shift in the exchange rate may be dominated by transactions, resulting in a decline in the trade balance. In the long term, this phenomena changes, and the quantities of exports and imports adapt, resulting in an increase in their elasticities and, as a result, a quantity change. As quantity changes, the international price of the devaluing country's exports falls, but the price of imported items rises, lowering demand (Eke, Eke and Obafemi, 2015).

The absorption approach, developed by Sidney Alexander and popularized by Miles, contends that depreciation of a country's currency may cause the terms of trade to deteriorate, shifting expenditure away from foreign goods and toward domestically produced goods, thereby improving the country's trade balance. It was created in response to the elasticity approach's more restrictive assumptions, and it emphasizes the macroeconomic impact of currency depreciation (Eke *et al.*, 2015).

The monetary approach, developed by Robert Mundell and Harry Johnson, became fully developed in the 1970s and views exchange rate-trade balance relations as a purely monetary phenomenon, positing that money plays an important role in the long run as both a disturbance and an adjustment in a country's balance of payment (Eke *et al.*, 2015). Consistent with this idea, the exchange rate is controlled by the intersection of two nations' supply and demand for money. The monetary model is based on the idea that devaluation decreases the actual worth of cash balances and/or changes in relative prices of traded and non-traded products, resulting in an improvement in the trade balance and the balance of payments (Eke *et al.*, 2015).

2.1.2 International Trade Theories

The theory of trade relevant in this study are the “absolute cost advantage” (ACA) and “comparative cost advantage” (CCA). The ACA is a classical economist's international trade theory. The ACA theory of international trade was developed by Adam Smith. Smith (1776) stated in his research of international trade that trade between countries is beneficial. Consistent with the theory, a

nation has an absolute advantage in producing a product when it is more efficient than any other country. As a result, if two countries specialize in producing different items (in which each has a distinct edge) and trade with one another, both countries will have more of both products accessible for consumption (Effiong and Okon, 2020). Consequently, trading relationships are mutually advantageous. International trade interactions, according to Smith, will result in mutually beneficial exchanges that will contribute to economic advancement. This traditional view promotes international trade as a driver of economic growth and progress (Effiong and Okon, 2020).

Consistent with the CCA trade theory, international trade benefits participating nations even if they have an absolute advantage in production. David Ricardo proposed this theory in 1817. In keeping with the CCA theory, even if a nation has an “absolute advantage” in producing two items over others, trade with the other country will still result in higher output for both countries than if the more efficient producer handled everything alone (Effiong and Okon, 2020). Consequently, the country with the absolute advantage in manufacturing both items would continue to produce both, but less of the one it will trade for, directing resources to the development of the one in which it has a comparative advantage (Viner, 1937 cited in Effiong and Okon, 2020).

2.2 Empirical Literature Review

The empirical literature relating to exchange rate, trade and economic growth has been conducted at both country-specific and cross-country bases. In a cross-country analysis conducted by Polterovich and Popov (2002), foreign exchange reserve accumulation was shown to be positively linked with GDP per capita growth and the level of the real exchange rate. Berg, Ostry, and Zettelmeyer (2008) investigated the elements that contribute to the sustainability of growth episodes in both emerging and established nations. They discovered that overvaluation of the real exchange rate has a negative impact on the length of growth.

Onafowora and Owoye (2008) used quarterly data from January 1980 to April 2001 to assess the influence of currency rate fluctuation on Nigerian exports to the United States. They used cointegration and the VECM framework. Empirical evidence suggests that in the long term, a unique cointegrating vector relating real exports, real foreign income, relative export prices, and real exchange rate volatility exists. Furthermore, heightened volatility in the real exchange rate exacerbated uncertainty regarding profit margins, which has a considerable negative impact on exports in both the short and long run. Their findings also demonstrate that increases in trade terms and actual foreign income have a favourable impact on export activity. Most crucially, they discovered that the post-1986 structural adjustment period's trade liberalization and economic reform measures aided Nigeria's export performance. Overall, the findings imply that measures aiming at obtaining and maintaining a stable competitive real exchange rate might help to increase Nigeria's exporting operations.

Using data from developing nations, Levy-Yeyati and Sturzenegger (2009) constructed two measures of foreign exchange intervention and discovered that they are positively connected (in separate regression models) with GDP growth and the level of the real exchange rate. The authors interpret the findings of these two studies as evidence that central banks in developing nations accumulate foreign currency reserves in order to maintain undervalued real exchange rates and therefore boost growth (Rapetti, Skott & Razmi, 2011).

Omojomite and Akpokodje (2010) examined the impact of exchange rate adjustments on Nigeria's trade performance from 1986 to 2007. The study was conducted in light of the fact that exchange rate reform (combined with trade policy reforms) was part of Nigeria's economic reform program, which was expected to diversify the economy's export base from oil to non-oil exports through competitiveness in the relative price of non-oil exports, as well as reduce imports, particularly of consumer goods. When the value of the country's currency is decreased through depreciation, it finds a tiny beneficial effect of exchange rate adjustments on non-oil exports. However, even after the implementation of exchange rate changes, the structure of imports, which is pro-consumer products, remained unaltered.

Oyinlola *et al.* (2010) used exports and imports functions to analyze the long-run and short-run effects of exchange rate and price changes on trade flows in Nigeria. On quarterly data from 1980Q1 to 2007Q4, the limits testing (Auto regressive distributive lag model) technique to cointegration was used. The findings show that relative prices, domestic and foreign income, nominal effective exchange rates, and the stock of external reserves all have a significant impact on Nigeria's trade flows, both in the short and long run. The results also demonstrated that, in the long term, devaluation is more successful than relative pricing in changing import demand in both baseline and enhanced models. In the case of export demand, however, the opposite is true.

Shehu and Youtang (2012) investigated the link between exchange rate volatility (ERV), trade flows, and economic development in Nigeria, a small open country. The empirical analysis is based on time series data from 1970 to 2009 and using time series econometrics technique. The findings show that ERV has a considerable impact on Nigerian trade flows. Their findings suggest the preference for a variable exchange rate regime over a fixed regime since it allows for larger trade flows to Nigeria. They advocated for the efficient diversification of the Nigerian economy by encouraging more manufacturing enterprises to produce enough to fulfil the demand of both domestic and regional West African markets, followed by the complete implementation of a floating exchange rate system.

Adeniran, Yusuf, and Adeyemi (2014) evaluated the influence of exchange rate variations on economic expansion in Nigeria from 1986 to 2013 and discovered that exchange rate fluctuations had a beneficial impact on economic growth. Fapetu and Oloyede (2014) studied the impact of foreign exchange management on Nigerian economic growth. The study's findings demonstrated a long-run association between economic growth, exchange rate, volume of exports, inflation, volume of imports, and foreign direct investment. Ayodele (2014) used the OLS method of multiple regression analysis to empirically evaluate the influence of exchange rates on the Nigerian economy. According to the findings of the analysis, exchange rate depreciation has a negative influence on economic growth because as the rate rises, economic growth suffers.

Khanom, Emu, Uddin, and Farhana (2014) examined the link between the exchange rate and the trade balance of Bangladesh from 1973 to 2011. Their estimated results show that there is a direct link between trade balance and exchange rate. They argue that the real exchange rate is an essential variable in trade balance, and that depreciation will enhance trade balance in the long term, thereby supporting the Marshall-Lerner condition. Wanhui (2014) examines the impact of nominal RMB exchange rate fluctuation on Chinese economic development from 1981 to 2012. The article indicates that exchange rate changes have a favourable long-run influence on import and export commerce.

Akpan and Atan (2015) evaluated the impact of exchange rate changes on Nigerian real output growth. The research investigates the possible direct and indirect association between exchange rates and GDP growth using quarterly data from 1986 to 2010. A simultaneous equations model within a fully specified macroeconomic model is used to determine the link in two methods. An approach known as the "Generalised Method of Moments" was utilized. Consistent with the estimation results, there is little indication of a substantial direct association between changes in the exchange rate and output growth. Rather, monetary variables have had a direct impact on Nigeria's economic growth. These variables have tended to maintain a real exchange rate structure that has been unfavourable to growth. The conclusion is that while reforms in exchange rate management are vital, they are insufficient to resurrect the Nigerian economy. To supplement the approved exchange rate strategy, a substantial program of economic transformation is necessary.

In their analysis, Eke, Eke, and Obafemi (2015) used yearly data to evaluate the influence of currency rates on Nigeria's balance of trade from 1970 to 2012. The study examined the connection using the real exchange rate and the Augmented Dickey Fuller test for unit root, the Johansen test for co-integration, and ECM were the technique of analysis. The co-integration test indicates that trade balances and the variables of interest have a long term connection. The result indicated that the exchange rate had a considerable negative impact on Nigeria's trade balance over the period. The

findings indicated that depreciation of the local currency did not help the country's balance of trade and hence balance of payments condition. As a result, it was advised that steps to stabilize the exchange rate and stop its continued free fall be carefully explored as a policy alternative.

Adelowokan, Adesoye, and Balogun (2015) investigated the impact of exchange rate fluctuation on Nigerian investment and growth between 1986 and 2014. To capture the relationships between the exchange rate, investment, interest rate, inflation, and growth during the period, the study used the VECM technique, cointegration, and ADF statistics for stationarity testing. Their findings indicate that there is a long-run link between the exchange rate, investment, interest rate, inflation, and growth. The study, however, discovered that exchange rate volatility had a detrimental impact on investment and growth. They advocate for the country's development of a sound exchange rate management system in order to facilitate economic growth.

Ali, Ajibola, Omotosho, and Adeleke (2015) examined the influence of Naira real exchange rate misalignment on Nigeria's economic expansion using quarterly data from 2000 to 2014. The estimations of Real Exchange Rate Misalignment (RERMIS) were obtained by analyzing deviations of the actual real exchange rate from a sustainable equilibrium path determined using Edwards' (1989) "Behavioural Equilibrium Exchange Rate" (BEER) technique. The study provided empirical support for RERMIS's detrimental influence on economic growth. This prompted them to advocate for the sustained adoption of market-based exchange rate arrangements to guarantee that the Naira's actual exchange rate follows its path of long-term stability.

The relationship between exchange rate volatility and economic growth in Nigeria was the topic of Amassoma and Odeniyi's (2016) research, with a particular emphasis on the buying power of typical Nigerians and the volume of international transactions. The study, which included econometric approaches such as Multiple Regression Analysis, the ADF test, the Johansen Co-integration test, and the ECM, backed up the conclusions of Adelowokan, Adesoye, and Balogun (2015) on the same issue. The study found that exchange rate variations had a beneficial, albeit minor, influence on economic growth in Nigeria in both the long and short run.

Augustine, John, and Emmanuel (2017) investigated the influence of the real effective exchange rate on the trade balances of eight nations using a variety of nonlinear methodologies. The findings of the asymmetric model for long-run cointegration analysis, short-run analysis, and half-lives show that exchange rate depreciation has a considerable impact on trade balance.

Abayomi, Adepoju, and Aasa (2017) used yearly time series data from 1981 to 2014 to investigate the impact of exchange rate changes on economic growth in Nigeria. The unit root test shows that all variables were $I(1)$, however the Johansen cointegration test shows a long run link between economic growth and the explanatory variables. In Nigeria, the Error Correction Model shows a negative short run causality flowing from nominal exchange rate to RGDP and from money supply increase to RGDP. The error correction term implies that 93.55% of deviations from long run equilibrium are rectified. As a result, the study advises that the government create export-oriented policies that would expedite the accumulation of foreign reserves to reverse or, at the very least, reduce exchange rate depreciation.

Onakoya, Aworinde, and Yinusa (2019) studied the existence of an asymmetric cointegrating link between Nigeria's exchange rate, trade balance, and growth from 1960 to 2016. The M-TAR (Momentum - Threshold Autoregressive) and TAR models were used in the study with the key assumption of the possibility of an unequal adjustment process in the disequilibrium. The results reveal that cointegration exists among the three variables in the TAR model. There is also an asymmetric adjustment disequilibrium process. The point estimates indicated that when the trade balance worsens, the adjustment pace slows. According to the asymmetric ECM, trade balance, real exchange rate, and growth all respond to disequilibrium, and the coefficients of domestic income and exchange rate are both negative. The report recommended that the government of Nigeria focus its policy efforts on an import substitution plan that will allow for the local manufacture of currently

imported commodities, hence providing long-term employment and the growth of Nigeria's industrial manufacturing sector.

Effiong and Okon (2020) investigated the contributions of foreign trade to Nigeria's economic development from 1981 to 2018. To determine the connections between the variables, the ARDL bounds test for cointegration and OLS approaches were utilized. During the era, the contribution of foreign trade to economic development was determined to be quite low. It was suggested that in order for Nigeria to gain from trade, the economy should be diversified and government institutions and agencies strengthened in order to restore sanity and faith in the system. Trade treaties must be scrutinized to verify that they are, by definition, advantageous to the economy.

Alasha (2020) examined the link between exchange rate fluctuations and their influence on Nigerian economic growth. The data in this study was analyzed using ordinary least squares regression. The study indicates that because exchange rate variations have a direct influence on the economy, an effective exchange rate regime must be developed. An effective exchange rate would assist to reduce inflation, improve Nigeria's trade balance, and increase Nigeria's production capacity, all of which are important pointers of good economic progress.

This study is therefore an attempt to add to the literature, on the influence of exchange rate and trade balance on economic growth in Nigeria from 1981 to 2020 using the ARDL approach.

Methodology

3.1 Model Specification

The model for this study is specified based on a disaggregated approach – total trade balance, oil trade balance, and non-oil trade balance; along with specifying the model that captures the determinants of exchange rate movements.

Model I: Effect of total trade balance and exchange rate on economic growth

$$RGDP = f(GFCF, LBR, INT, GOVT, ECHR, TTBL) \quad \text{Equation 3.1}$$

Where RGDP captures the growth rate of real gross domestic product, GFCF is the growth rate of gross fixed capital formation, LBR reflects the labour force growth, INT is the interest rate, GOVT is government expenditure as a ratio of GDP, ECHR reflects the exchange rate, and TTBL is the growth in total trade balance measured as the difference between total export and total imports.

Transforming Equation 3.1 to an econometric form;

$$RGDP_t = \gamma_0 + \gamma_1 GFCF_t + \gamma_2 LBR_t + \gamma_3 INT_t + \gamma_4 GOVT_t + \gamma_5 ECHR_t + \gamma_6 TTBL_t + \mu_{1t} \quad \text{Equation 3.2}$$

Where γ_0 is the constant term, γ_1 to γ_6 are the parameters, and μ_{1t} is the error term.

Model II: Effect of oil trade balance and exchange rate on economic growth

$$RGDP = f(GFCF, LBR, INT, GOVT, ECHR, OTBL) \quad \text{Equation 3.3}$$

Where the variables are as earlier defined and OTBL represents the growth in oil trade balance. Transforming Equation 3.3 into an econometric form;

$$RGDP_t = \delta_0 + \delta_1 GFCF_t + \delta_2 LBR_t + \delta_3 INT_t + \delta_4 GOVT_t + \delta_5 ECHR_t + \delta_6 OTBL_t + \mu_{2t} \quad \text{Equation 3.4}$$

Where δ_0 is the constant term, δ_1 to δ_6 are the parameters, and μ_{2t} is the error term.

Model III: Effect of non-oil trade balance and exchange rate on economic growth

$$RGDP = f(GFCF, LBR, INT, GOVT, ECHR, NTBL) \quad \text{Equation 3.5}$$

Where the variables are as earlier defined and NTBL represents the growth in non-oil trade balance. Transforming Equation 3.5 into an econometric form;

$$RGDP_t = \pi_0 + \pi_1 GFCF_t + \pi_2 LBR_t + \pi_3 INT_t + \pi_4 GOVT_t + \pi_5 ECHR_t + \pi_6 NTBL_t + \mu_{3t} \quad \text{Equation 3.6}$$

Where π_0 is the constant term, π_1 to π_6 are the parameters, and μ_{3t} is the error term.

Model IV: Determinants of exchange rate movements in Nigeria

$$ECHR = f(RGDP, INT, ERES, INF, TTBL) \quad \text{Equation 3.7}$$

Where the variables are as earlier defined, INT is interest rate and ERES represents the volume of external reserves. Transforming Equation 3.7 into an econometric form;

$$ECHR_t = \varphi_0 + \varphi_1 RGDP_t + \varphi_2 INT_t + \varphi_3 ERES_t + \varphi_4 INF_t + \varphi_5 TTBL_t + \mu_{4t} \quad \text{Equation 3.8}$$

Where φ_0 is the constant term, φ_1 to φ_5 are the parameters, and μ_{4t} is the error term.

3.2 Sources of Data

The data is time series in nature which covers 1981 to 2020. The time period so selected has covered significant aspect of the policies of the government in the management of exchange rate and other macroeconomic variables. The data were gotten from Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin and the World Bank database. The data sources are reliable and valid because they are from official publication.

3.3 Analytical Technique

Given the fact that our study utilizes time series data which may be influenced by time, we follow the systematic step by step procedure. We start by ascertaining the time series properties of the variables using the augmented Dickey-Fuller unit root test under the constant and linear trend assumption. The unit root test equation, in its general form, is specified as follows:

$$\Delta M_t = \alpha_0 + \delta t + \beta_1 M_{t-1} + \sum_{i=0}^n \rho_i \Delta M_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \quad \text{Equation 3.9}$$

Where M is the time series variable to be tested for existence of unit root, α_0 captures the constant, δ captures the coefficient of the trend, t is the time trend, i is the number of lags to be automatically selected based on Akaike Information Criterion (AIC), Δ is the difference operator, β_1 is the coefficient to be tested for unit root, ρ_i captures the augmented portion of the test, and ε is the error term. The null hypothesis is that $\beta_1 = 1$ against the alternative hypothesis that $\beta_1 \neq 0$.

We thereafter proceed to detecting the existence of a long run relationship among variables in the model. To do this, the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) bonds test for cointegration is being utilized. The existence of cointegration (levels relationship) will then propel us to estimating both the short-run and long run coefficients using the error correction model. The equation for the ARDL model is specified thus;

$$\Delta P_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=0}^m \beta_i \Delta M_{t-i} + \sum_{i=0}^n \gamma_i \Delta Q_{t-i} + \phi ECM_{t-1} + \mu_t \quad \text{Equation 3.10}$$

In Equation 3.10, P is the dependent variable while Q is captures all the explanatory variables; m and n are the optimal lags for the dependent and explanatory variables respectively; β_i and γ_i are the parameters to be estimated; θ captures the speed of adjustment of the short-run disequilibrium to long-run equilibrium relationship; ECM reflects the error correction mechanism; and μ is the error term that is assumed to be “white-noise”.

Empirical Results

4.1 Stylized Facts on Trade Balance and Exchange Rate Movements in Nigeria

For the period 1981 to 2020, the core variables of interest have been exhibiting different behaviours (positive and negative) and Table 1 captures such changes.

Table 1

Output growth, trade balance and exchange rate movements in Nigeria for selected years

Year	Real GDP Growth (%)	Oil Trade Balance (in ₦ Billions)	Non-Oil Trade Balance (in ₦ Billions)	Trade (in ₦ Billions)	Total Trade Balance (in ₦ Billions)	Trade Exchange Rate (₦/\$1)
1981	-13.13	10,560.70	-12,377.00		-1,816.30	0.61
1985	5.91	11,171.90	-6,513.70		4,658.20	0.89
1990	11.78	100,553.40	-36,385.20		64,168.20	8.04
1995	-0.07	771,739.40	-576,205.70		195,533.70	21.89
2000	5.02	1,700,082.71	-739,381.80		960,700.91	102.11
2005	6.44	6,343,279.98	-1,897,601.51		4,445,678.47	132.15
2010	8.01	9,494,738.01	-5,667,595.56		3,827,142.45	150.30
2015	2.65	6,429,786.71	-8,649,335.18		-2,219,548.48	193.28
2019	2.21	15,553,920.06	-16,190,770.03		-636,849.97	306.92
2020	-1.79	9,015,510.90	-17,183,926.74		-8,168,415.84	358.81

Source: Extracted from CBN Statistical Bulletin, 2020.

Table 1 reflects the value of our key variables of interest for selected years. the economy experienced a negative economic growth rate of -13.13% as at 1981 followed by an exchange rate of ₦0.61/\$1. Also, a positive oil trade balance of ₦10,560.70 billion and a negative non-oil trade balance of ₦12,377.00 billion was recorded the same period. This huge negative trade balance wiped out the surplus in the current account, thus giving a negative total trade balance of ₦1,816.30 billion. The economy recovered steadily by recording a positive economic growth rate of 5.91% and 11.78% for 1985 and 1990 respectively. The two periods so mentioned was followed by a positive total trade balance of ₦4,658.20 billion and ₦64,168.20 billion respectively. This was because the surplus in the oil trade balance offset the native non-oil trade balance for the two periods. Meanwhile, the domestic currency depreciated to ₦0.89/\$1 and ₦8.04/\$1 for the two periods respectively.

The economy enjoyed a continuous increase in the total trade balance as a result of an increasing oil trade balance despite of the huge negative trade balance form the non-oil sector till 2010. However, the domestic currency has been declining drastically from ₦21.89/\$1 in 1995 to ₦150.30/\$1 as at 2010. Consequently, the rate of economic growth has been experiencing positive rates from 2000 till 2019. For the period 2015, 2019 and 2020, the Nigerian economy witnessed a negative total trade balance all through amounting to ₦2,219,548.97 billion and ₦8,168,415.84 billion for 2015 and 2020 respectively. The exchange rate continued to depreciate drastically from ₦193.28/\$1 in 2015 to ₦358.81/\$1 in 2020. As at 2020, the rate of economic growth declined to -1.79% due to the Covid-19 pandemic. This effect was also

observed from the reduction in the oil demand which crippled the oil trade balance from ₴15,553,920.06 billion in 2019 to ₴9,015,510.90 billion in 2020. Similarly, the non-oil trade deficit worsened between the two period by increasing from ₴16,190,770.03 billion in 2019 to ₴17,183,926.74 billion in 2020.

4.2 Descriptive Properties of the Series

The descriptive statistics of the key variables of interest, namely: real GDP growth rate (RGDP), growth in total trade balance (TTBL), growth in oil trade balance (OTBL), growth in non-oil trade balance (NTBL), and exchange rate (ECHR) are reflected in Table 2. It covers the mean up to the test for normality using the Jarque-Bera statistic.

Table 2

Descriptive statistics of the variables					
	RGDP	TTBL	OTBL	NTBL	ECHR
Mean	3.441026	37.97150	33.72267	31.24731	103.4434
Maximum	15.33000	1182.628	387.3304	400.6557	358.8108
Minimum	-10.9200	-525.7566	-48.1701	-34.5511	0.672867
Std. Dev.	4.845054	260.0566	80.06216	72.89341	100.7390
Skewness	-0.4442	1.879748	2.665446	3.628565	0.858177
Kurtosis	4.188327	11.39689	11.57103	18.37224	2.951413
Jarque-Bera	3.577216	137.5426	165.5565	469.5790	4.790879
Observations	39	39	39	39	39

Source: Researchers' Computation (2022)

For the thirty-nine (39) years' time span considered in the study, RGDP averaged 3.44% with a maximum of 15.33% and a minimum of -10.92%. The variable has a standard deviation of 4.85% with a negative skewness coefficient of -0.44, reflecting that the variable has been tilting towards smaller values over the years. Similarly, TTBL averaged 37.97% with a maximum and minimum values of 1,182.63% and -525.76% respectively. Its standard deviation was 260.06% with a positive skewness coefficient of 1.88. This implies that the growth in total trade balance has been tilting towards greater values.

The growth in oil trade balance (OTBL) averaged 33.72% with its minimum and maximum values of -48.17% and 387.33% respectively. The standard deviation seems to be quite high (80.06%) with a positive skewness coefficient of 2.67 reflecting that the oil trade balance has been on the high side most often. The growth in non-oil trade balance (NTBL) has a mean value of 31.25% with a standard deviation of 72.89%. The maximum and minimum values were 400.66% and -34.55% respectively. The skewness coefficient of 3.63, which is positive, is an indication that its value has been on the rise over time. The ECHR has a mean value of ₴103.44/\$1 with a standard deviation of ₴100.74/\$1. Its maximum and minimum values were respectively ₴358.81/\$1 and ₴0.61/\$1; while value of the variable were tilting to greater values as reflected in the positive skewness coefficient of 0.86. This captures the continuous depreciation of the domestic currency over the years.

4.3 Correlation Analysis

To check whether the variables correlates among themselves, the correlation matrix in Table 3 reflects the correlation coefficients of the different variables of interest

From Table 3, there is a positive correlation between RGDP and the trade and exchange rate variables. However, such correlation is weak as none of them reaches a meagre 0.50. Also, the trade and exchange rate variables has weak correlation with each other, reflecting the fact that multicollinearity could not be a problem in the model. Total trade balance correlates positively with every other variable, but OTBL and NTBL correlates negatively with ECHR.

Table 3

Correlation result					
	RGDP	TTBL	OTBL	NTBL	ECHR
RGDP	1				
TTBL	0.0204	1			
OTBL	0.0441	0.1885	1		
NTBL	0.0101	0.2296	0.8298	1	
ECHR	0.1031	0.0928	-0.1882	-0.1509	1

Source: Researchers' Computation (2022)

4.4 Unit Root Test

To ascertain the time series properties of the variables, the augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test is employed, while the Philip-Peron (PP) test is utilized as a confirmatory test. The test is conducted using the constant and trend assumption. The result is captured in Table 4 where our inference is drawn from the PP test since it is considered to be more potent.

Table 4

Unit root test result						
Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test			Philip-Peron (PP) Test			
Variables	ADF Statistic	5% Critical Value	PP Statistic	5% Critical Value	Order of Integration	
RGDP	-3.5981	-3.5330	-10.995	-3.5366	I(0)	
GFCF	-5.2038	-3.5366	-5.1864	-3.5366	I(1)	
LBR	-5.0820	-3.5577	-6.552	-3.5403	I(1)	
INT	-5.0644	-3.5529	-9.8831	-3.5366	I(1)	
GOVT	-10.038	-3.5366	-11.124	-3.5366	I(1)	
ECHR	-4.6544	-3.5366	-4.4603	-3.5366	I(1)	
ERES	-4.5742	-3.5366	-5.3218	-3.5403	I(1)	
NTBL	-7.3346	-3.5330	-7.3633	-3.5330	I(0)	
OTBL	-5.4025	-3.5366	-8.5233	-3.5330	I(0)	
TTBL	-3.6391	-3.5403	-8.7037	-3.5366	I(1)	

Source: Researchers' Computation (2022)

From the result in Table 4, it is noticed that our variables are stationary in mixed order. some at first difference, I(1), while orders are integrated at levels, I(0). RGDP, NTBL, and OTBL are all stationary at level while other variables were stationary after differencing them once. Since our variables are stationary at mixed order of levels and first difference, the appropriate technique to be followed is the ARDL approach. This leads us to ascertaining the existence of cointegration among the variables using the ARDL bounds test for cointegration.

4.5 Test for Cointegration

The bounds test is conducted to ascertain the existence of levels relationship among the variables. The test result is presented in Table 5. The test is conducted using the F-statistic. If the F-statistic is outside the upper and lower bounds, at 5% level of significance, then cointegration exist.

Table 5

ARDL bounds test result for levels relationship

Models	Test Statistic	F-Statistic	Number of Parameters (K)	5% Critical Lower Bounds I(0)	5% Critical Upper Bounds I(1)
Model I	F-statistic	6.9261*	6	2.27	3.28
Model II	F-statistic	3.0888	6	2.27	3.28
Model III	F-statistic	2.7671	6	2.27	3.28
Model IV	F-statistic	7.1821*	5	2.39	3.38

Source: Researchers' Computation (2022)

The test result so conducted is reflected in Table 5 based on the four models estimated in this study. For Model I, the F-statistic of 6.9261 is greater than the 5% lower bounds (2.27) and the 5% upper bound (3.28) statistic. As such, cointegration exist in Model I. This implies that we will estimate both the short-run and long-run estimates for Model I. For Model II, the F0statistic of 3.0888 is just greater than the 5% lower bound of 2.27 but less than the 5% upper bound of 3.28. as such, cointegration does not exist. We will therefore estimate just the short-run estimates. The similar case is for Model III where the F-statistic is less than the 5% upper bound. In Model IV, cointegration exist since the F-statistic of 7.1821 is greater than both the 5% upper and low bounds. We will then estimate both the long-run and short-run estimates for Model IV using the ARDL error correction model.

4.6 ARDL Short-Run Error Correction Mechanism

In line with the result of the cointegration test conducted, the result of the short-run estimates, and the long-run estimates in some cases, are reflected thereof, given the respective models specified for the study – Model I, Model II, Model III, and Model IV. The estimation follows the ARDL error correction model which shows how the short-run disequilibrium in the models are adjusted in order to attain equilibrium in the long-term.

Model I: Influence of total trade balance and exchange rate on economic growth

Table 6

ARDL error correction model for Model I

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Statistic	Probability
D(GFCF)	-0.5918	0.0760	-7.7879	0.0000
D(GFCF(-1))	-0.2503	0.0805	-3.1105	0.0067
D(GFCF(-2))	-0.2666	0.0657	-4.0572	0.0009
D(INT)	0.8918	0.0906	9.8421	0.0000
D(INT(-1))	0.6404	0.1014	6.3177	0.0000
D(GOVT)	-0.2967	0.2073	-1.4315	0.1715
D(GOVT(-1))	1.5363	0.2529	6.0748	0.0000
D(GOVT(-2))	0.4105	0.1904	2.1553	0.0467
D(ECHR)	-0.0510	0.0178	-2.8599	0.0113
D(ECHR(-1))	-0.0270	0.0251	-1.0740	0.2988
D(ECHR(-2))	0.0710	0.0203	3.4993	0.0030
D(TTBL)	0.0039	0.0011	3.7116	0.0019
CointEq(-1)*	-0.7631	0.0855	-8.9247	0.0000
R-squared	0.9036		S.E. of regression	1.7285
Adjusted R-squared	0.8533		Durbin-Watson stat	2.1841

Source: Researchers Computation (2022)

The result of the first model capturing the effect of total trade balance indicates that total trade has a positive and significant effect on economic growth at the 1% level of significance given the p-value of 0.0019 ($p < .05$). It follows that trade has been beneficial to growth as postulated in the comparative cost advantage. Consistent with the coefficient of 0.0039, a unit percent increase in total trade balance will increase economic growth by 0.0039% on the average. Meanwhile, exchange rate has wielded a negative and significant short-run effect on growth at the 5% level of significance given its p-value of 0.0113 ($p < .05$). This is in line with the earlier argument in the literature that “exchange depreciation can be harmful to growth”. The continuous decline in the value of the naira due to its mono-product nature in the international market could not in any way be expected to stimulate growth. From the coefficient (-0.051), a unit percent increase in exchange rate will lead to a 0.051% decrease in growth on the average. While a one-period lag in exchange rate fuelled a negative but insignificant effect on growth, its two-period lag exerted a positive and significant effect at the 5% level. As such, the exchange rate as at two years behind supported growth by increasing growth by 0.071% on the average.

The GFCF along with its one-period and two-period lags yielded a negative and significant effect on growth at the 5% level. This is against the required sign that capital should generate growth. Such negative effect could be traced to high degree of abandoned projects that could add to the capital stock of the nation, implying waste of resources over time. A unit percent increase in GFCF will reduce RGDP 0.5918% on the average. The one-period and two-period lags of GFCF reduced growth by 0.2503% and 0.2666% respectively. Changes in interest rate (ΔINT) and its one-period lag exerted a positive and significant effect on growth. This implies that the present rate of interest is sustainable for growth. Hence, a unit percent increase in INT leads to a 0.08918% increase in growth; while the one-period lag in INT increases growth by 0.6404% on the average.

Changes government expenditure as a percentage of GDP exerted a negative but insignificant effect on growth. However, its one-period and two-period lags wielded a positive and significant effect on growth. As such, they increased growth by 1.5363% and 0.4105% respectively.

The error correction term possesses the required sign (negative) and is statistically significant at the 1% level. It implies from the coefficient of the ECM that 71.631% of the short-run imbalance in economic growth is corrected annually for long-run equilibrium to be restored. The r-squared of 0.9036 implies that all the variables explains 90.36% of the total variations in economic growth in Nigeria during the study period.

Model II: Influence of exchange rate and oil trade balance on economic growth

For Model II where we capture the effect of oil trade balance on economic growth, the result is portrayed in Table 7. From the result, the one-period lag of RGDP exerts a positive and significant effect on RGDP. This implies that the previous year's RGDP reduces current year's GDP by 0.22%, consistent with the coefficient. Gross fixed capital formation also exerts a negative and significant effect on growth. From the coefficient, a unit percent increase in capital yields a 0.2227% decrease in RGDP. Interest rate and its one-period lag also exerts a positive and significant effect on RGDP at the 1% level of significant. A unit percentage increase in interest rate yields a 0.5245% increase in RGDP. Similarly, the one-period lag of interest rate increased RGDP by 0.6086% on the average.

Changes in exchange rate is noted to wield a negative and significant effect on RGDP at the 1% level of significance. It follows that a unit percent increase in exchange rate reduced RGDP by 0.0758% on the average. Also, oil trade balance exerts a negative and significant effect on RGDP at the 1% level of significance. Thus, a unit percent increase in OTBL leads to a 0.0113% decrease in RGDP on the average. This result does not go in accordance with the fact that trade promotes growth. This could be linked to the vagaries inherent in the international oil market and the current Covid-19 pandemic that has undermined the potency of oil trade in fostering productivity in an economy.

Table 7

ARDL error correction model for Model II

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Statistic	Probability
D(RGDP(-1))	-0.2200	0.0985	-2.2334	0.0355
D(GFCF)	-0.2227	0.0842	-2.6448	0.0145
D(INT)	0.5245	0.1123	4.6716	0.0001
D(INT(-1))	0.6086	0.1103	5.5197	0.0000
D(ECHR)	-0.0758	0.0187	-4.0559	0.0005
D(OTBL)	-0.0113	0.0035	-3.2505	0.0035
CointEq(-1)*	-0.5166	0.0910	-5.6772	0.0000
R-squared	0.8081		S.E. of regression	2.2718
Adjusted R-squared	0.7697		Durbin-Watson stat	2.4556

Source: Researchers Computation (2022)

The error correction mechanism indicates that 51.66% of the short-run distortions in the model is corrected per year for the restoration of equilibrium in the long-run. The coefficient is negative and statistically significant as required. The r-squared reflects that taking only oil revenue into consideration, along with other explanatory variables, the model explains 80.80% of the total variations in RGDP.

Model III: Influence of exchange rate with non-oil trade balance economic growth

For Model III where the result is reflected in Table 8, changes in GFCF exerts a positive though an insignificant effect on RGDP. Its one-period lag exerts a negative but insignificant effect. However, its two-period lags and three-period lags wielded a negative and significant effect on RGDP at the confidence level of 5%. Thus, the two-period lags of GFCF decreased RGDP by 0.3515% while its three-period lags decreased RGDP by 0.4940% on the average.

Changes in labour force exerted a negative but insignificant effect on RGDP. Such negative effect could be linked to high rate of unemployment and underemployment of labour within the Nigerian economy. Also, its one-period lag to three-period lags wielded a negative but insignificant effect on RGDP. Changes in interest rate along with its lags exerted positive and significant effect on RGDP. A unit percent increase in INT increases RGDP by 0.5465% on the average. Its one-period lag increased RGDP by 1.2525% while its three-period lags increased growth by 0.9568% on the average.

Changes in GOVT is also noted to exhibit a negative and significant effect on RGDP while its lag values wielded a positive and significant effect. A unit percent increase in GOVT reduced RGDP by 2.9127% on the average. Its one-period lag and three-period lags increased RGDP by 0.4854% and 1.3391% on the average respectively.

Changes in ECHR and its two-period lags is observed to wield a positive but insignificant effect when the non-oil trade balance is inserted into the model. Meanwhile, the one-period lag and three-period lags of exchange rate yielded a negative and significant effect on RGDP. In that regards, the one-period lag and three-period lags of ECHR reduced RGDP by 0.1630% and 0.2132% respectively. It is also observed that changes in non-oil trade balance and its one-period to three period lags exerted a negative and significant short-run effect on RGDP at the 5% level of significance. A unit percent increase in NTBL wields a 0.0239% decrease in RGDP. Also, the one period lag, two-period lags, and three-period lags of NTBL reduces RGDP by 0.0754%, 0.0433% and 0.0350% respectively. This negative and significant effect is not surprising coupled with the fact that the non-oil trade balance has remained on the negative throughout the study period, implying an unfavourable balance of trade.

ARDL error correction model for Model III

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Statistic	Probability
D(GFCF)	0.3872	0.1852	2.0909	0.1277
D(GFCF(-1))	-0.1334	0.1026	-1.3008	0.2842
D(GFCF(-2))	-0.3515	0.0790	-4.4500	0.0211
D(GFCF(-3))	-0.4940	0.1075	-4.5955	0.0194
D(LBR)	-1.3156	4.9629	-0.2651	0.8081
D(LBR(-1))	-16.9487	8.5557	-1.9810	0.1419
D(LBR(-2))	-13.2328	9.4164	-1.4053	0.2546
D(LBR(-3))	23.9504	7.6909	3.1141	0.0527
D(INT)	0.5465	0.0959	5.7010	0.0107
D(INT(-1))	1.2525	0.1408	8.8942	0.0030
D(INT(-2))	0.4830	0.1550	3.1162	0.0526
D(INT(-3))	0.9568	0.1535	6.2353	0.0083
D(GOVT)	-2.9127	0.3703	-7.8668	0.0043
D(GOVT(-1))	0.4854	0.2218	2.1885	0.1164
D(GOVT(-2))	0.6032	0.2167	2.7843	0.0687
D(GOVT(-3))	1.3391	0.2405	5.5690	0.0114
D(ECHR)	0.0074	0.0193	0.3819	0.7280
D(ECHR(-1))	-0.1630	0.0250	-6.5132	0.0074
D(ECHR(-2))	0.0418	0.0254	1.6444	0.1986
D(ECHR(-3))	-0.2132	0.0313	-6.8119	0.0065
D(NTBL)	-0.0239	0.0061	-3.8879	0.0302
D(NTBL(-1))	-0.0754	0.0111	-6.7628	0.0066
D(NTBL(-2))	-0.0433	0.0081	-5.3748	0.0126
D(NTBL(-3))	-0.0350	0.0067	-5.1971	0.0138
CointEq(-1)*	-1.1271	0.1312	-8.5902	0.0033
R-squared	0.9747		S.E. of regression	1.2943
Adjusted R-squared	0.9139		Durbin-Watson stat.	2.3316

Source: Researcher's Computation (2022)

The error correction term (-1.1271) indicates that 112.71% of the short-run distortions in the model is corrected annually for equilibrium to be restored. The implication here is that it takes less than a year for the model to be fully restored to equilibrium level. The r-squared reflects that 97.47% of the total variation in RGDP is explained by variations in non-oil trade balance plus other variables captured in the model.

Model IV: Determinants of Exchange Rate Movements in Nigeria

In Model IV, we estimate the economic determinants of exchange rate movements in Nigeria. Table 9 captures the result of our findings.

Consistent with Table 9, changes in RGDP, ERES and INF are observed to have a negative and significant short-run effect on exchange rate movement in Nigeria at the 1%, 1% and 5% level of

significance level. a unit percent increase in these three variables decreases exchange rate by 3.6956%, 0.1898%, and 0.5048% respectively. This is an indication that increased productivity within the domestic economy will help to cut down heavy importation and promote exports. This will encourage foreign exchange inflow, leading to the appreciation in the value of the domestic currency. Also, the available of sufficient external reserves will support the needed foreign exchange needs of the domestic economy, and this will reduce the high demand for forex in the forex market. This will act as a check on the value of the dollar currency relative to the naira. Meanwhile, the one-period lag and two period lags of INF exerts a positive and significant effect on ECHR movements in Nigeria as they increase ECHR by 0.6023% and 0.5269% respectively. This implies that previous years' inflation has been detrimental to value of the domestic currency vis-à-vis the dollar.

Table 9

ARDL error correction model for Model IV

Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Statistic	Probability
D(RGDP)	-3.6956	0.623584	-5.92641	0.0000
D(ERES)	-0.1898	0.038831	-4.88945	0.0001
D(INF)	-0.5048	0.183737	-2.74784	0.0117
D(INF(-1))	0.6023	0.160964	3.742252	0.0011
D(INF(-2))	0.5269	0.195536	2.694899	0.0132
D(TTBL)	-0.0020	0.007848	-0.25686	0.7997
D(TTBL(-1))	-0.0364	0.011125	-3.2754	0.0035
CointEq(-1)*	-0.0305	0.003815	-7.99915	0.0000
R-squared	0.64276		Durbin-Watson stat	1.335048
Adjusted R-squared	0.553449		S.E. of regression	12.97006

Source: Researchers' Computation (2022)

Changes in total trade balance exerts a negative but insignificant effect on ECHR movements while its one-period lag wielded a negative and significant effect. Thus, the previous year's TTBL reduced exchange rate by 0.0364% on the average. This is an indication that stimulating trade (especially exports) will help to ensure the appreciation of the naira over time. The coefficient of the ECM (-0.0305) which is negative and statistically significant at the 1% significance level meets the requirement for the adjustment ability of the model. Thus, 3.05% of the short-run distortions in the model is corrected annually for equilibrium to be restored. However, the speed of adjustment is very slow, implying that it will take approximately thirty-three years for equilibrium to be fully restored. The r-squared of 0.64276 implies that 64.28 of the total variations in exchange rate movements in Nigeria is explained by variations in economic growth rate, external reserves, inflation, and total trade balance (current account balance).

4.7 Long-Run Estimate

The long-run result is presented for only the models that cointegration exist. Based on the Bounds test, cointegration existed for Model 1 and Model IV.

For Model I where we capture the influence of exchange rate and total trade balance on economic growth, Table 10 reflects the long-run result. From the result, GFCF still exerts a negative effect on RGDP though such effect is not significant. Labour force exerts a positive and significant effect on RGDP. Meaning that as LBR increases by 1%, RGDP increases by 7.5419% on the average. This points out the importance of human capital accumulation on the growth process of an economy.

Table 10

Long-run result for Model I				
Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Statistic	Probability
GFCF	-0.0774	0.1169	-0.6620	0.5174
LBR	7.5419	2.3717	3.1799	0.0058
INT	0.6097	0.3304	1.8451	0.0836
GOVT	-1.2885	0.7908	-1.6294	0.1228
ECHR	-0.0157	0.0256	-0.6148	0.5473
TTBL	0.0213	0.0063	3.3551	0.0040
C	-393.4639	124.1848	-3.1684	0.0060

Source: Researchers' Computation (2022)

Interest rate exerts a positive but insignificant effect on RGDP while the effect of GOVT is negative and insignificant. Similarly, ECHR wielded a negative but insignificant effect on RGDP. Conversely, total trade balance (TTBL) exerts a positive and significant long-run influence on RGDP at the 5% level of significance. A unit percent increase in TTBL generates a 0.0213% increase in RGDP. The constant term implies that holding all the variables in the model constant, the economy will experience a negative growth rate of -39.4639% in the long-run.

Table 11

Long-run result for Model IV				
Variable	Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Statistic	Probability
RGDP	0.6100	4.2773	0.1426	0.8875
INT	0.5651	4.9792	0.1135	0.9103
ERES	-0.3562	0.2720	-1.3097	0.1993
INF	-2.3671	1.1507	-2.0572	0.0476
TTBL	0.0613	0.0622	0.9851	0.3317
C	140.6791	74.9210	1.8777	0.0693

Source: Researchers' Computation (2022)

In Table 11, the long-run result of Model IV is presented to reflect on the determinants of exchange rate movements in Nigeria. It is observed that RGDP, TTBL and INT exerted a positive but insignificant long-run influence on ECHR movement in Nigeria. Meanwhile, ERES external reserves exerted a negative but insignificant effect while INF exerted a negative and significant effect. Thus, a unit percent increase in INF reduces ECHR by 2.3671% on the average. It has been argued that inflation is a key economic variable that influences both the domestic economy and hitherto exerts a significant influence on the external sector through the exchange rate. Such effect can be traced through the purchasing power parity. The currency having a higher degree of inflation depreciates while the one with low rate of inflation appreciates. But such depreciation will make exports cheaper and imports dearer, leading to more exports and a resulting accumulation of forex which will hitherto lead to an appreciation of the domestic currency in the long-run.

4.8 Major Findings and Discussion

From the analysis, the major findings of the study are as highlighted as follows:

- Total trade balance has a positive and significant effect on economic growth both in the short-run and in the long-term. This means that a favourable trade balance is desired to drive up economic growth in Nigeria.
- Oil trade balance and non-oil trade balance has a negative and significant effect on economic growth. This is an indication that depending on a mono-product export will not drive economic growth to the desired level. Rather, diversifying our export base is key for long-term growth.
- Exchange rate exerts a negative and significant effect on economic growth. This means that the continuous depreciation of our domestic currency relative to the US dollar do not support the Nigeria's strive for growth, pointing out the need for exchange rate stability.
- The short-run exchange rate movements in Nigeria has been driven by economic growth, external reserves, inflation, and lags in current account balance (total trade balance). But in the long-run, the determining factor of exchange rate movement is the rate of inflation. Consistent with this, stimulating domestic production, managing a substantial external reserves, ensuring price stability, and maintaining a favourable current account balance are the yardstick to which the naira exchange rate to the dollar could be stable and at a favourable rate.

Conclusion and Recommendation

It is the desire of any nation to achieve economic growth and a favourable balance of payments as captured in the core macroeconomic objectives. Nigeria, over the years has been facing economic changes which has resulted to different degrees of growth rate and exchange rates. The trade situation has often been more of oil exports and less of non-oil exports. This has led to increasing unfavourable trade balance in the non-oil sector, with some years of positive trade balance within the oil sector. In that regards, this study examined the influence of trade balance and exchange rate movements in Nigeria from 1981 to 2020. We utilized the ARDL approach to ascertain both the short-run and long-run effect of trade balance and exchange rate on growth; as well as the determinants of exchange rate movements in Nigeria. We disaggregated our model on trade balance into three – total trade balance, oil trade balance, and non-oil trade balance - to detect which of them has any influence on growth.

From our analysis, the unit root test conducted based on the ADF and PP approaches revealed that our variables were integrated in mixed order of levels and first difference. consequently, we used the Bounds test for levels relationship to ascertain whether cointegration exist. From the Bounds test, two out of our four models (Model I and Model IV) reflects the existence of cointegration. Thus, we estimate both the short-run and long-run estimates for Model I (capturing the effect of total trade balance and exchange rate on economic growth) and Model IV (capturing the determinants of exchange rate movements in Nigeria). In Model I, we observed that exchange rate has a negative and significant short-run effect on economic growth while total trade balance has a positive and significant effect. But in the long-run, exchange rate has a negative but insignificant effect while total trade balance still wielded a positive and significant effect on economic growth. The r-squared showcased that the explanatory variables only explains 90.36% of the total variations in RGDP. This represents a good fit of the regression line.

In Model II, both exchange rate and oil trade balance exerted a negative and significant effect on economic growth, showing their deleterious effect on growth over the years. the r-squared showed that the explanatory variables explains 80.81% of the total variation in RGDP. This is quite a good fit of the regression line. Model III reflects the fact that exchange rate and its lags yielded a negative and significant effect on growth. Similarly, non-oil trade balance and its lags also exerted a negative and significant short-run effect on growth. the r-squared indicated that the explanatory variables accounts for 97.47% of the total variations in economic growth. This is also a good fit. In Model IV, the short-run determinants of exchange rate movements in Nigeria include economic growth, external reserves, inflation, and total trade balance as

they exerted significant influence on growth. But in the long-run, the only variable that drives exchange rate movement is the rate of inflation in the domestic economy.

Consequent upon the findings of this study, the following recommendations are given:

- There is need to drive the economy to export more. This can be achieved through massive diversification of the economy into solid minerals and agriculture with greater value chain. In this way, Nigeria will be able to diversify her export base to drive home massive foreign exchange. This because, as statistics indicates as at 2018, 94% of export products are crude petroleum, 2% floating structures for breaking up and 2% natural gas (Trade Update Data, 2019). More international ties should be strengthened among other West African countries as it is indeed a fact that Nigeria's export to other African countries outside ECOWAS is 55% (Trade Update Data, 2019).
- To ensure exchange rate stability, domestic production should be accelerated to deepen exportation and curtail excessive importation of goods that could be produced locally. The import substitution industrialization strategy should further be strengthened. Further, there is need to curtail excessive depletion of the external reserves as it has a significant role to play in times of emergency needs for foreign exchange. Finally, inflation should be checked to ensure price stability by utilizing a mix of monetary and fiscal policy measures.

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